

Drilling Lexico-Semantic Knowledge in Portuguese from BERT

Hugo Gonalo Oliveira^[0000–0002–5779–8645]

CISUC, Department of Informatics Engineering
University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal
`hroliv@dei.uc.pt`

Abstract. We compiled a set of patterns that denote lexico-semantic relations in Portuguese, created templates where one argument is fixed and the other is replaced by a mask, and then used BERT for predicting the latter. For most relations and measures, when assessed in a test of lexico-semantic analogies, BERT predictions outperformed those of earlier methods computed from static word embeddings, either with a pattern alone or with a combination of patterns. There is still a large margin of progression, but this suggests that BERT can be used as a source of lexico-semantic knowledge in Portuguese.

Keywords: BERT, Masked Language Model, semantic relations, lexico-semantic knowledge, lexical patterns

1 Introduction

Whether it is for the creation or for the enrichment of lexical knowledge bases (LKBs) like WordNet [8], there is a long research history on the automatic acquisition of lexico-semantic knowledge from textual corpora. Following the seminal work of Hearst [17], much relies on lexico-syntactic patterns where related words tend to co-occur, e.g., “ X_1 , such as X_2 ”, for `hypernymyOf(X_1 , X_2)`. Nowadays, some of those patterns can be easily tested in masked language models (MLMs) like a pre-trained BERT [4], with some authors suggesting that these large models could be used as knowledge bases [22].

In order to analyse to what extent this shortcut works, specifically for Portuguese lexico-semantic relations, we explore BERTimbau [25], a BERT model pre-trained for Portuguese. More precisely, we compiled a set of lexical patterns for the acquisition of such relations, and then created templates by presetting one argument (X_1) and masking the other, to be predicted by BERT. The quality of the predictions, based on three different measures (accuracy, accuracy@10, MAP), was assessed with TALES [14], a dataset of lexico-semantic analogies in Portuguese, and compared with that of two earlier methods, applied on a GloVe model for Portuguese [16]. Besides each pattern individually, we further assessed the benefits of combining the predictions of different patterns, considering their score and rank. Performance varied amongst different relations and patterns, and was especially high in the acquisition of hypernyms of concrete concepts. Still, for

each relation, there was at least one pattern or combination that outperformed both baselines in at least one measure.

The interesting results suggest that a pre-trained BERT is indeed a great source of lexico-semantic knowledge, faster and possibly more focused than raw corpus search. Yet, even if it may boost the search for related words to include in a LKB, for the sake of accuracy, this would still require additional filtering.

In the remainder of the paper, we overview work on the automatic acquisition of lexico-semantic relations; describe the proposed approach and the experimentation setup; and, before concluding, report on the obtained results.

2 Related Work

Early work on the automatic acquisition of lexico-semantic relations from text follows the work of Hearst [17], where a set of lexico-syntactic patterns denoting hyponymy was presented. To minimise human intervention, some proposed to improve precision and recall of the extractions, e.g., by computing the cosine similarity of the arguments [2]; or learning the patterns automatically, not only for hyponymy [24], but also other relations [21], respectively using distant and weak supervision, with seed examples from WordNet [8]. All the previous targeted English, but rule-based approaches for acquiring hyponymy [9], part-of [18], and other relations [13] were also applied to Portuguese text.

In models of distributional semantics, such as word embeddings, relations are not explicit, but analogies [19] have been computed for a broad range of syntactic and semantic relations, including lexico-semantic [5]. Besides the unsupervised discovery of hypernymy instances [3], the performance of simple analogy was improved by learning to compute related words from multiple examples [5]. The previous were also applied to Portuguese word embeddings, and used to solve lexico-semantic analogies in this language [14]. Despite their low accuracy in these relations, predictions can still be useful for enriching wordnets [15].

Currently, transformer-based models, like BERT [4] or GPT [23], are the paradigm in Natural Language Processing. They are also not ready for explicitly retrieving semantic relations, but provide a shortcut for earlier corpora-based approaches, i.e., they are pre-trained in large collections of text and are good at filling blanks [22, 7], completing sentences [23], or computing their likelihood [11, 20], including of those matching the aforementioned patterns. It is thus no surprise that BERT has been assessed for the presence of relational knowledge [22], having in mind its utilisation as a knowledge base; or for relation induction [1], starting with a small number patterns and seeds; even if it suits better some relations than others [7].

Recent work [20] exploited BERT for detecting hyponymy pairs in Portuguese. This is however slightly different from our goal, because, instead of scoring the likelihood of two words forming a hyponymy pair, we aim to predict hypernyms, as well as other related words, for a given word.

3 Experimentation Setup

To some extent, the process of acquiring relations from corpora based on lexical patterns can be simulated with a masked language model (MLM). This has two main advantages: it does not require to process the full corpus for each pattern; and it will retrieve the most likely words, not any value found.

An important difference is that common MLMs predict a single token, meaning that: (i) predictions will never be multiword expressions; (ii) one relation argument has to be fixed in the pattern. So, the problem is better framed as the acquisition of words x_2 , given a template that uses x_1 , such that instance $relation(x_1, x_2)$ holds. For instance, the lexical pattern “a x_2 is a type of x_1 ” typically indicates $hypernym(x_1, x_2)$. Thus, to acquire hyponyms of *animal*, x_1 and x_2 are respectively replaced by the word **animal** and the [MASK] token. Expected predictions for x_2 would be *dog*, *horse* or *human*.

Following this, we explored BERTimbau [25] (base), a BERT model pre-trained for Portuguese, and tested templates based on different lexical patterns for acquiring lexico-semantic relations that one would find in a LKB. This section provides some considerations on the patterns used, and further describes the dataset, the metrics, and the baselines used for evaluation.

3.1 Considerations on the Patterns

Available literature was our starting point [9, 13] for compiling useful patterns, but a broader set was crafted to cover different relations, also trying to control some limitations of this approach. Specifically, we avoid patterns that lead to predictions like punctuation signs or non-content words (e.g., determiners, prepositions); or in the plural (e.g., “ X_1 e outros [MASK]”, for hypernyms of X_1), so that lemmatisation is not necessary. We considered patterns using both the masculine and feminine determiners, and avoided those starting with [MASK].

For instance, pattern “[MASK] ou outro X_1 ” could be used for acquiring hyponyms of X_1 , but with $X_1 = veículo$, we get the top-5 predictions: *Um*, *Gol*, *Moto*, *Uma*, *ou*. The majority is capitalised, and only one is good enough (*Moto*). If we change the pattern to “**um** [MASK] ou outro X_1 ”, we get: *carro*, *caminhão*, *automóvel*, *veículo*, *ônibus*, where only one is incorrect (*veículo*). Moreover, since starting with the determiner ‘*um*’ constrains the predictions to masculine words, we add a second pattern “**uma** [MASK] ou outro X_1 ”. This results in additional predictions: *moto*, *bicicleta*, *pessoa*, *van*, *aeronave*, four of which correct (all but *pessoa*). We could further add patterns starting with the definite articles ‘*a*’ and ‘*o*’ but, from our experience, they would not add much.

A similar example is the pattern “**o** X_1 **tem** [MASK]” for acquiring parts of X_1 . With $X_1 = computador$, we get: *.*, *?*, *que*, *;*, [UNK], including punctuation signs, a preposition and the unknown token. Of course we can ignore these, as we did for punctuation signs, but a more fruitful strategy was to include similar patterns with an article before the mask. For instance, “**o** X_1 **tem um** [MASK]” results in *teclado*, *computador*, *programa*, *problema*, *processador*; and “**o** X_1 **tem uma** [MASK]” in *função*, *tela*, *interface*, *memória*, *câmera*.

An average of 12 patterns were compiled for each of the 14 target relations, totalling 169 patterns. The full list of patterns was made publicly available¹ for anyone willing to use or expand it, and several examples are included in Table 1.

3.2 Dataset

To assess different methods and patterns in the acquisition of lexico-semantic knowledge, we used TALES [14], a dataset originally developed for assessing lexico-semantic analogies in Portuguese, obtained from several LKBs. TALES has the same format as BATS [10], i.e., for each relation, it includes 50 entries with two columns: a word (source) and a list of related words split by a ‘/’ (target). An example for hyponym-of(source, target) is: *gua lquido/substncia*.

Patterns were compiled for each of the 14 different relations in TALES, including four symmetric – synonym between nouns, verbs and adjectives; antonyms between adjectives – and ten non-symmetric – purpose-of (e.g., *abrir-chave*) and has-purpose (*lpis-escrever*); abstract (*valor-preo*), concrete (*ave-papagaio*) and verb (*permitir-aprovar*) hypernyms; abstract (*ano-perodo*), concrete (*arma-instrumento*) and verb (*explicar-dizer*) hyponyms; part-of (*mo-corpo*) and has-part (*casa-sala*). We used version 1.1² of TALES, which has the same contents as the original, but target words are re-ordered by the number of LKBs they were found in (roughly, confidence).

3.3 Metrics

A common measure for assessing word embeddings in analogy tasks is the accuracy [19, 5]. It computes the proportion of entries x'_1 for which the first prediction x'_2 is correct. However, this is too restrictive for most lexico-semantic relations (e.g., a hypernym has many hyponyms; or an object might have several parts), especially if the final goal is to create or enrich a knowledge base. Therefore, we compute two additional measures that consider the top-10 predictions: Accuracy@10 (Acc@10), more relaxed, which counts the answer as correct as long as one of the top-10 predictions is correct; and Mean Average Precision@10 (MAP), which accounts for the number of correct predictions and their ranking. The latter is especially suitable to a scenario like ours, where more than one correct prediction often exists.

3.4 Baselines

Performance achieved with the patterns was compared with that of 3CosAvg and LRCos [5], two methods with a similar purpose, but applied to word embeddings learned from corpora, here a 300-sized GloVe model for Portuguese [16], which previously showed to be the best in semantic analogies [16, 14]. Given any number

¹ https://github.com/NLP-CISUC/PT-LexicalSemantics/blob/master/Patterns/BERT_patterns_for_TALES.txt

² <https://github.com/NLP-CISUC/PT-LexicalSemantics/tree/master/TALESv1.1>

of (x_1, x_2) pairs, such that $relation(x_1, x_2)$ holds, and any argument x'_1 , their goal is to find suitable values of x'_2 , such that $relation(x'_1, x'_2)$ holds.

3CosAvg (eq. 1) computes the average vector offset in all other available relations of the same type (in TALEs, $50 - 1 = 49$). LRCos (eq. 2) considers the similarity of x'_2 to x'_1 and the probability of x'_2 belonging to the same class as other target words (x_2), in relations of the same type. We implemented both methods and, as Drozd et al. [5], used a Logistic Regression classifier for computing the probability in LRCos, trained with positive examples taken from the first target word of every entry of the dataset, except x'_2 . Pairs of random words were used as negative examples.

$$x'_2 = \operatorname{argmax}_{w \in V} \cos(w, x'_1 + avg_offset) \quad (1)$$

$$x'_2 = \operatorname{argmax}_{w \in V} P(w \in class(x_2)) * \cos(w, x'_1) \quad (2)$$

4 Performance with Different Patterns

With TALEs as our reference, we select the target relation and: (i) go through each entry; (ii) predict the target word(s), given the source; (iii) compute evaluation scores of predictions against the target word(s). For 3CosAvg and LRCos, the relation is learned from all (x_1, x_2) pairs in TALEs, except the current one. Predictions for x'_2 are obtained given the source word x'_1 . For the lexical patterns, X_1 is replaced by the source word and BERT predicts tokens for the mask.

Although patterns were compiled for 14 relations, we noted that, for the symmetric (synonym and antonymy), baselines were hard to beat. Exceptions were: “ou X_1 ou [MASK]”, for antonymy ($Acc = 0.30$, $Acc@10 = 0.42$, $MAP = 0.33$, against 0.20, 0.46, 0.28 by LRCos); and “ X_1 é o mesmo que [MASK]”, for synonymy between verbs ($Acc = 0.12$, $Acc@10 = 0.80$, $MAP = 0.28$, against 0.26, 0.62, 0.32 by LRCos). We tested different lexical patterns (e.g., “ X_1 é a mesma coisa que [MASK]” or “ X_1 é sinónimo de [MASK]” for synonymy), but similarity – better modelled with the cosine of the embeddings of each word than with a single template – plays an important role in these relations.

This section is focused on the other ten (non-symmetric) relations, namely on the best patterns, their performance and of their combination.

4.1 Single Patterns for Non-Symmetric Relations

For each non-symmetric relation in TALEs, Table 1 reports on a selection of patterns, covering the best for each measure, also including their scores and of the baselines. It is clear that performance varies significantly, depending on the relation and on the pattern. Part, has-part, and purpose-of relations are the most challenging, followed by hyponymy between abstract nouns. This happens both for baselines and lexical patterns. For all but one non-symmetric relation (hyponymy between concrete nouns), there is at least one pattern that outperforms

both baselines in at least one measure, suggesting that BERT can be a better source of lexico-semantic knowledge than static word embeddings, at least concerning non-symmetric relations³.

It is interesting to note that, depending on the type of arguments (abstract or concrete nouns, verbs), the best patterns for hyponymy and hypernymy vary. The top performance is achieved for hyponymy between concrete nouns, namely with the well-known pattern “ X_1  um tipo de [MASK]”. This is in line with previous work for English [7], where BERT performed particularly well in the acquisition of hypernyms⁴. Relations of this kind include `hyponymOf(txi, veculo)` and `hyponymOf(rosa, flor)`.

4.2 Combining the Best Patterns

Despite some interesting results, the best pattern is not always the same, not only for different measures, but also for variations of the same relation (hypernymy). So, in order to maximise the outcomes, one would have to combine the predictions of different patterns. This is especially true for patterns that constrain the gender of the predictions (see Section 3.1). If there are target words of both genders, we will hardly get them all from a single pattern of those.

We thus tested two different methods of combining predictions by different patterns. Both consider the top- n predictions by the top- m patterns, but differ on the ranking criteria. The Score method ranks all the predictions according to the sum of their BERT-assigned scores⁵ with each considered pattern. The Borda method disregards the scores and only considers the ranking of each prediction for each pattern, by applying the Borda [6] voting scheme, i.e., for each pattern, a prediction ranked r will get the score of $n - r + 1$.

Table 2 reports on the performance of both combination methods, with $n = 10$ and two different values for m , $m = 3$ and $m = 5$, considering the best patterns according to the MAP measure. For easier comparison, their scores are put together with those of the best baseline(s) and pattern(s). When there is not a pattern that stands out as the best, we include the scores of the two best. On the right-hand side, a table has the overall performance, based on the average for the 50 entries of each non-symmetric relation in TALEs.

There are improvements, but not a straightforward best combination method for every single relation, while overall performance is close for any of the four combinations. When compared to the best patterns, both overall Acc and

³ Even though both the models and the methods applied are significantly different, we note that the BERT model used was pre-trained in a corpus with nearly twice the number of tokens as the GloVe model used. This is still relevant for less experienced users, or when nor time nor resources are available for training of new models, limiting the choice to what is available out-of-the-box.

⁴ TALEs is organised in files where the source (first column) is related to the target (second). So, in the Hyponymy file, `hyponymOf(source, target)` holds, and consequently `hypernymOf(target, source)`. Since we are predicting the targets, this file is used for assessing hypernym prediction.

⁵ BERT predictions are always ranked according to a score also given by the model.

Relation	Method / Pattern	Acc	Acc@10	MAP
Purpose-of	3CosAvg	0.08	0.28	0.12
	LRCos	0.10	0.32	0.16
	preciso de uma [MASK] para X_1	0.10	0.22	0.13
	uma [MASK] serve para X_1	0.08	0.20	0.11
	preciso de um [MASK] para X_1	0.12	0.16	0.13
Has-Purpose	3CosAvg	0.24	0.40	0.29
	LRCos	0.24	0.40	0.29
	uma X_1 é usada para [MASK]	0.20	0.42	0.26
	um X_1 é usado para [MASK]	0.20	0.38	0.24
	uma X_1 serve para [MASK]	0.06	0.24	0.10
Hypernym-of (abstract)	3CosAvg	0.06	0.58	0.22
	LRCos	0.08	0.56	0.20
	se X_1 é hiperónimo de [MASK]	0.20	0.66	0.27
	um [MASK] ou outra X_1	0.22	0.64	0.31
	a [MASK] é uma espécie de X_1	0.24	0.56	0.28
Hypernym-of (concrete)	3CosAvg	0.16	0.54	0.27
	LRCos	0.18	0.50	0.25
	um [MASK] ou outra X_1	0.14	0.54	0.20
	um [MASK] ou outro X_1	0.16	0.46	0.23
	uma [MASK] ou outro X_1	0.14	0.40	0.21
Hypernym-of (verbs)	3CosAvg	0.08	0.46	0.16
	LRCos	0.20	0.48	0.27
	como [MASK] e outros modos de X_1	0.08	0.54	0.18
	como [MASK] e outras maneiras de X_1	0.10	0.48	0.19
	como [MASK] ou outras maneiras de X_1	0.12	0.42	0.17
Hyponym-of (abstract)	3CosAvg	0.06	0.36	0.11
	LRCos	0.08	0.38	0.14
	X_1 é um tipo de [MASK]	0.14	0.52	0.23
	X_1 é hipónimo de [MASK]	0.14	0.52	0.21
	X_1 ou outro [MASK]	0.14	0.42	0.21
Hyponym-of (concrete)	3CosAvg	0.12	0.60	0.26
	LRCos	0.28	0.56	0.34
	X_1 é um tipo de [MASK]	0.54	0.88	0.58
	X_1 ou outro [MASK]	0.20	0.60	0.30
	um [MASK], como X_1	0.22	0.58	0.32
Hyponym-of (verbs)	3CosAvg	0.16	0.52	0.23
	LRCos	0.20	0.54	0.26
	como X_1 ou outras maneiras de [MASK]	0.24	0.64	0.30
	como X_1 e outras maneiras de [MASK]	0.18	0.56	0.23
	como X_1 ou outros modos de [MASK]	0.10	0.44	0.17
Part	3CosAvg	0.02	0.30	0.09
	LRCos	0.06	0.28	0.11
	um [MASK] tem X_1	0.12	0.30	0.17
	um [MASK] possui X_1	0.08	0.24	0.14
	o X_1 do [MASK].	0.12	0.22	0.15
Has-Part	3CosAvg	0.06	0.22	0.09
	LRCos	0.06	0.24	0.09
	o X_1 possui uma [MASK].	0.08	0.34	0.17
	um [MASK] é uma parte de X_1	0.12	0.28	0.17
	a [MASK] é uma parte de X_1	0.06	0.22	0.10

Table 1. Performance of different methods and patterns for non-symmetrical relations.

Acc@10 increase and MAP is matched. There is no relation for which a baseline is the best in the three measures, but, for two (has-purpose and hyponymy verbs), the best Acc and MAP are still by LRCos. Additionally, for three relations, there were no improvements over using the best pattern (has-purpose, hyponym-of concrete and verbs).

Relation	Method	Acc	Acc@10	MAP
Purpose-of	LRCos	0.10	0.32	0.16
	Best pattern	0.10	0.22	0.13
	Score-3	0.08	0.30	0.20
	Borda-3	0.08	0.30	0.16
	Score-5	0.14	0.30	0.16
	Borda-5	0.08	0.32	0.14
Has-Purpose	3CosAvg / LRCos	0.24	0.40	0.29
	Best pattern	0.20	0.42	0.26
	Score-3	0.22	0.38	0.26
	Borda-3	0.18	0.40	0.25
	Score-5	0.20	0.34	0.25
	Borda-5	0.20	0.36	0.25
Hypernym-of (abstract)	3CosAvg	0.06	0.58	0.22
	LRCos	0.08	0.56	0.20
	Best pattern	0.20	0.66	0.27
	Best pattern 2	0.22	0.64	0.31
	Score-3	0.28	0.76	0.32
	Borda-3	0.38	0.74	0.34
Hypernym-of (concrete)	Score-5	0.32	0.74	0.31
	Borda-5	0.34	0.74	0.32
	3CosAvg	0.16	0.54	0.27
	LRCos	0.18	0.50	0.25
	Best pattern	0.14	0.54	0.20
	Best pattern 2	0.16	0.46	0.23
Hypernym-of (verbs)	Score-3	0.26	0.54	0.29
	Borda-3	0.18	0.56	0.23
	Score-5	0.22	0.54	0.24
	Borda-5	0.18	0.52	0.23
	LRCos	0.20	0.48	0.27
	Best pattern	0.08	0.54	0.18
Hyponym-of (abstract)	Best pattern 2	0.10	0.50	0.18
	Score-3	0.10	0.54	0.19
	Borda-3	0.10	0.56	0.19
	Score-5	0.12	0.52	0.19
	Borda-5	0.10	0.52	0.19
	LRCos	0.08	0.38	0.14
Hyponym-of (concrete)	Best pattern	0.14	0.52	0.23
	Score-3	0.22	0.60	0.25
	Borda-3	0.16	0.56	0.24
	Score-5	0.22	0.60	0.24
	Borda-5	0.14	0.68	0.23
	3CosAvg	0.12	0.60	0.26
Hyponym-of (verbs)	LRCos	0.28	0.56	0.34
	Best pattern	0.54	0.88	0.58
	Score-3	0.50	0.86	0.51
	Borda-3	0.52	0.84	0.54
	Score-5	0.42	0.86	0.46
	Borda-5	0.46	0.86	0.49
Part	LRCos	0.20	0.54	0.26
	Best pattern	0.24	0.64	0.30
	Score-3	0.20	0.58	0.22
	Borda-3	0.18	0.56	0.23
	Score-5	0.16	0.54	0.20
	Borda-5	0.16	0.52	0.19
Has-Part	3CosAvg	0.02	0.30	0.09
	LRCos	0.06	0.28	0.11
	Best pattern	0.12	0.30	0.17
	Score-3	0.12	0.30	0.17
	Borda-3	0.16	0.30	0.18
	Score-5	0.14	0.40	0.20
Has-Part	Borda-5	0.16	0.30	0.18
	LRCos	0.06	0.24	0.09
	Best pattern	0.08	0.34	0.17
	Best pattern 2	0.12	0.28	0.17
	Score-3	0.14	0.44	0.22
	Borda-3	0.08	0.46	0.17
Overall	Score-5	0.14	0.40	0.21
	Borda-5	0.10	0.40	0.19
	Method	Acc	Acc@10	MAP
	3CosAvg	0.11	0.43	0.19
	LRCos	0.13	0.44	0.22
	Best pattern Acc	0.21	0.45	0.26
Best pattern Acc@10	0.19	0.50	0.25	
Best pattern MAP	0.20	0.47	0.27	
Score-3	0.22	0.52	0.27	
Borda-3	0.21	0.52	0.26	
Score-5	0.22	0.52	0.26	
Borda-5	0.21	0.51	0.25	

Table 2. Performance of best methods and the combination of patterns for non-symmetrical relations.

5 Conclusions

In what may be seen as yet another contribution for better understanding BERT and what we can do with it, we have explored a Portuguese BERT model in the acquisition of lexico-semantic relations. After manually compiling lexical patterns that denote the relations of interest, templates were obtained by fixing one argument, while the other was a mask, to be predicted by BERT’s MLM. Predic-

tions by each pattern were assessed in a dataset of lexico-semantic analogies and compared to baselines that exploit static word embeddings. Either with a single pattern or by a combination, baselines were outperformed for most relations. The best performance was in the acquisition of hypernyms of concrete nouns.

Improvements confirm that a pre-trained BERT can be useful for boosting the creation or enrichment of LKBs, but probably not in a completely automatic fashion, because not all predictions are accurate. This is especially true for parts of concepts, concepts of parts, or concepts with a specific purpose. For better accuracy, results may have to be further filtered by humans or by dedicated automatic procedures.

To improve the current results, compiled patterns can be tested with other models in the future. In fact, we can give a word on two initial experiments with BERT-large and GPT-2 fine-tuned for Portuguese⁶. The former led to improvements in hypernymy and hyponymy between verbs and abstract nouns, also synonymy between verbs, but had even lower performance for part and has-part, while struggling to beat the baselines in the same relations as BERT-base. For GPT-2, templates⁷ had to be slightly modified and were more limited – i.e., the prediction is the first generated word – so performances were significantly lower.

We did consider a broad range of patterns, but others, possibly acquired automatically from corpora as in Bouraoui et al. [1], may be tested in the future. It is also in our plans to analyse how well the BERT-computed likelihood of sentences that instantiate semantic relations correlates with relation prototypicality and whether it can be used as a confidence score, e.g., how it correlates with the number of lexical resources where a relation instance is found [12].

Acknowledgements This work was funded by the project POWER (grant number POCI-01-0247-FEDER-070365), co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund (FEDER), through Portugal 2020 (PT2020), and by the Competitiveness and Internationalization Operational Programme (COMPETE 2020); and by national funds through FCT, within the scope of the project CISUC (UID/CEC/00326/2020) and by European Social Fund, through the Regional Operational Program Centro 2020. It is also based upon work from COST Action CA18209 Nexus Linguarum, supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology). <http://www.cost.eu/>.

References

1. Bouraoui, Z., Camacho-Collados, J., Schockaert, S.: Inducing relational knowledge from BERT. In: Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence. pp. 7456–7463. AAAI Press (2020)
2. Cederberg, S., Widdows, D.: Using LSA and noun coordination information to improve the recall and precision of automatic hyponymy extraction. In: Proceedings of the Seventh Conference on Natural Language Learning at HLT-NAACL 2003. pp. 111–118 (2003)

⁶ <https://huggingface.co/pierreguillou/gpt2-small-portuguese>

⁷ Patterns for GPT available from https://github.com/NLP-CISUC/PT-LexicalSemantics/blob/master/Patterns/GPT_patterns_for_TALES.txt

3. Chang, H.S., Wang, Z., Vilnis, L., McCallum, A.: Distributional inclusion vector embedding for unsupervised hypernymy detection. In: Proceedings of the 2018 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies, Volume 1 (Long Papers). pp. 485–495 (2018)
4. Devlin, J., Chang, M.W., Lee, K., Toutanova, K.: BERT: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding. In: Proceedings of 2019 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies. pp. 4171–4186. ACL (2019)
5. Drozd, A., Gladkova, A., Matsuoka, S.: Word embeddings, analogies, and machine learning: Beyond king - man + woman = queen. In: Proceedings the 26th International Conference on Computational Linguistics: Technical papers COLING 2016. pp. 3519–3530. COLING 2016 (2016)
6. Emerson, P.: The original Borda count and partial voting. *Social Choice and Welfare* 40(2), 353–358 (Feb 2013)
7. Ettinger, A.: What BERT is not: Lessons from a new suite of psycholinguistic diagnostics for language models. *Transactions of the ACL* 8, 34–48 (2020)
8. Fellbaum, C. (ed.): *WordNet: An Electronic Lexical Database (Language, Speech, and Communication)*. The MIT Press (1998)
9. de Freitas, M.C., Quental, V.: Subsídios para a elaborao automtica de taxonomias. In: *Anais do XXVII Congresso da SBC*. pp. 1585–1594 (2007)
10. Gladkova, A., Drozd, A., Matsuoka, S.: Analogy-based detection of morphological and semantic relations with word embeddings: what works and what doesn’t. In: *Procs of NAACL 2016 Student Research Workshop*. pp. 8–15. ACL (2016)
11. Goldberg, Y.: Assessing BERT’s syntactic abilities. arXiv:1901.05287 (2019)
12. Gonalo Oliveira, H.: A survey on Portuguese lexical knowledge bases: Contents, comparison and combination. *Information* 9(2) (2018)
13. Gonalo Oliveira, H., Costa, H., Gomes, P.: Extraco de conhecimento lxico-semntico a partir de resumos da Wikipdia. In: *Proceedings of INFORUM 2010, Smpsio de Informtica*. Braga, Portugal (September 2010)
14. Gonalo Oliveira, H., Sousa, T., Alves, A.: TALES: Test set of Portuguese lexical-semantic relations for assessing word embeddings. In: *Procs of ECAI 2020 Workshop on Hybrid Intelligence for Natural Language Processing Tasks (HI4NLP 2020)*. CEUR Workshop Proceedings, vol. 2693, pp. 41–47. CEUR-WS.org (2020)
15. Gonalo Oliveira, H., Aguiar, F.S.d.S., Rademaker, A.: On the Utility of Word Embeddings for Enriching OpenWordNet-PT. In: *Proceedings of 3rd Conference on Language, Data and Knowledge (LDK 2021)*. OASICS, vol. 93, pp. 21:1–21:13. Schloss Dagstuhl – Leibniz-Zentrum fr Informatik, Dagstuhl, Germany (2021)
16. Hartmann, N.S., Fonseca, E.R., Shulby, C.D., Treviso, M.V., Rodrigues, J.S., Alusio, S.M.: Portuguese word embeddings: Evaluating on word analogies and natural language tasks. In: *Proceedings of 11th Brazilian Symposium in Information and Human Language Technology (STIL 2017)*. pp. 122–131 (2017)
17. Hearst, M.A.: Automatic acquisition of hyponyms from large text corpora. In: *Proceedings of 14th Conference on Computational Linguistics*. pp. 539–545. COLING 92, Association for Computational Linguistics, Morristown, NJ, USA (1992)
18. Markov, I., Mamede, N., Baptista, J.: Automatic Identification of Whole-Part Relations in Portuguese. In: *Proceedings of 3rd Symposium on Languages, Applications and Technologies*. OASICS, vol. 38, pp. 225–232. Schloss Dagstuhl–Leibniz-Zentrum fuer Informatik (2014)
19. Mikolov, T., Chen, K., Corrado, G., Dean, J.: Efficient estimation of word representations in vector space. In: *Proceedings of Workshop track of ICLR* (2013)
20. Paes, G.E.: *Deteco de Hipernimos com BERT e Padres de Hearst*. Master’s thesis, Universidade Federal de Mato Grosso do Sul (2021)

21. Pantel, P., Pennacchiotti, M.: Espresso: Leveraging generic patterns for automatically harvesting semantic relations. In: *Procs of 21st International Conference on Computational Linguistics and 44th annual meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*. pp. 113–120. ACL Press, Sydney, Australia (2006)
22. Petroni, F., Rocktäschel, T., Riedel, S., Lewis, P., Bakhtin, A., Wu, Y., Miller, A.: Language models as knowledge bases? In: *Proceedings of 2019 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing and 9th International Joint Conference on Natural Language Processing (EMNLP-IJCNLP)*. pp. 2463–2473. ACL (2019)
23. Radford, A., Wu, J., Child, R., Luan, D., Amodei, D., Sutskever, I.: Language models are unsupervised multitask learners. *OpenAI Blog* 1(8), 9 (2019)
24. Snow, R., Jurafsky, D., Ng, A.: Learning syntactic patterns for automatic hypernym discovery. *Advances in neural information processing systems* 17, 1297–1304 (2005)
25. Souza, F., Nogueira, R., Lotufo, R.: BERTimbau: Pretrained BERT models for Brazilian Portuguese. In: *Proceedings of Brazilian Conference on Intelligent Systems (BRACIS 2020)*. LNCS, vol. 12319, pp. 403–417. Springer (2020)